

A REVIEW OF THE ROLE OF YOGASANAS IN MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS

***Dr. Kiran A. Chavhan**

Assistant Professor Dept. of Rachana Sharir, PACH Vadodara.

Article Received on 26 April 2026,
Article Revised on 16 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20443209>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Kiran A. Chavhan

Assistant Professor Dept. of Rachana
Sharir, PACH Vadodara.

How to cite this Article: *Dr. Kiran A. Chavhan (2026). A Review Of The Role Of Yogasanas In Management Of Diabetes Mellitus. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 213–221.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the common lifestyle disorders of 21st century. It is caused by breach complex of genetic, behavioral and environmental factors which result into insulin resistance, decreased glucose utilization, and increased glucose production. The worldwide prevalence of DM has increased dramatically over the past two decades. From an estimated 30 million cases in 1985 to 177 million in 2000, it is believed that 7368 million individuals will have diabetes by the year 2030. India is likely to become global capital of diabetes in next few years. To counteract these conditions, The Indian system of medicine has a valuable history of *Yoga*. Amongst the *Ashtang Yoga* described by *Patanjali*, *yogasana* today are being widely accepted globally. *Asanas* have great prospective to change patho-physiology of our body. It increase the blood and oxygen

supply to various organs which also increase the efficacy and functioning of them. Diabetes is mainly associated with malfunction of endocrine part of pancreas. Consistent practice of *Aasans* like *Bhujangasan*, *Matsyasan*, *Paschimottanasan*, *Chakrasan*, *Vajrasan*, *Dhanurasan* etc have immense results in controlling diabetes along with medications. When not managed in proper time and with a holistic approach it becomes a major cause of blindness, kidney failure, stroke, and lower limb amputation. Thus to explore these beneficial effects of *yogasan* for diabetic patients, this study was initiated and through literature related to topic was reviewed from all available sources along with a holistic approach to put forth a fair conclusion.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes Mellitus, *Yogasanas*, Lifestyle Disorders.

INTRODUCTION

In Modern era, sedentary life-style and drastic changes in food pattern are leading cause of the disease such as Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertention, Obesity etc. Diabetes Mellitus is known to be a slow killer in world affecting most of the population in different age group. Prevalence rate of diabetes has risen from 108 million in 1980 to 422million in 2014. The global prevalence of diabetes among adults over 18 years of age has risen from 4.7%in 1980 to 8.5% in 2004. It prevalence has been rising more rapidly in middle –and low income countries. In 2016, an estimated 1.6 million deaths were directly caused by diabetes.^[1] WHO estimates that diabetes was the seventh leading cause of death in 2016. According to Diabetes Atlast 2006 published by the International Diabetes Federation, the number of people with diabetes in India currently are around 40.9 million and is expected to raise to 69.9million by 2025 unless urgent preventive step are taken. Diabetes is group of metabolic disorders that is impaired insulin secretion and insulin resistance, hyperglacemia, polydipsia, polyuria and hyperphagia, added metabolic dysregulation in the form of deranged lipid profile.^[2] Only medicinal management is not sufficient for treating Diabetes. Lifestyle modification and yogic exercise have also proven the best modality in this case. Man is in constant pursuit for health, happiness and peace, since it is the key to health, success and salvation. The purpose of *yoga* is to harmonize body, mind and spirit so that they function with complete harmony.^[3] *Yoga* has given patients the hope to reduce medication besides slowing the progression of the disease. And thus the world is looking towards *yoga* as a better management for diabetes mellitus along with *Ayurveda*.

MATERIAL AND METHODES

The text of *swasthavritta* and *Yoga, Samhitas* related to *yoga* were mainly referred for this study. Supportive texts of contemporary science were also utilized. Recent Research papers and literature from internet was also studied critically. Since DM is most emerging problem of India from two past decades and has no absolute solution in contemporary science the efforts are done to find any adjuvant treatment for the same.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

In this ‘stressful-age’ due to modernization and mechanization, human being bears a great amount of mental stress. And this is exactly where *Yoga* play a very important role in averting and treating them. *Yoga* is not science of particular field, it is science of Human life itself. *Yoga* is the practical way to attain salvation. Body, mind and soul are like pillars of

healthy life which is the secret of our ancient science.

Yoga brings control over *the Manovrutti* viz. *Kshipta* Mudha, *vishipta*, *Ekagra*, and *Nirodha*^[4] *Asana* is third among *Ashtang yoga* told by *Patanjali*. *Aasana* mean: *Sthir sukhasana*: i.e. to seat in stable and comfortable posture. *Aasana* is body posture of well being useful for meditation because *Aasanasiddhi* get control over *mana*, natural urges and climate.^[5]

In *Hathyoga* by practicing *Aasana* the body is placed in different way in specific posture in such way that the vital organs and endocrine gland rehabilitate and start functioning better than before. It gives strength, lightness of body and health. Relaxation through constant practice of *Aasana* and blending self with infinite i.e. *Ananta* are attained by mastery over *Aasana*.^[6] *Asana* brings stability in mind and body. Lord *shiva* narrated total 84 *Aasana*.^[7] *Yogasana* may be broadly classified into three categories. 1. Meditative *Aasanas* – These are posture which are considered conducive to the practice of meditation. ie, *Dhyan*. 2. Relaxing *Asana* - These are the posture which produce mental and physical relaxation such as *Shavasana*, *Makarasana*, etc. 4. Cultural or Corrective *asanas* e.g. *Sheershasan*

Aasana & there effects^[10,11]

1] *Ardhamatsyendrasana*

Effects- Spine – stretch is well obtained, Lung ventilation is improved, and the abdominal circulation, digestion, and excretion are improved. Kidneys and Urinary bladder are toned up.

Benefits - Abdominal fat is reduced, beneficial in diabetes, Dyspepsia and constipation are corrected, Leucorrhoea in female are relived, help to awaken *Kundalini*, gives moon power to man.

2] *Matsyendrasana*

Effects – According to *Hathyogaprdipika* this *aasana* is effective in *Agnivardhan* & improved digestion, *Kundilini* operational, cure chronic illness, stability of moon.

3] *Shirshasana*

Effects –Improved Nervous system, Digestive system and prominent physical, endocrine and Metabolic beneficiary changes is lowered,

4] Dhanurasana

Effects- mind become calm and quiet, stimulate the abdominal organs, beneficial in stress disorder.

5] Chakrasana

Tones abdominal organs, stimulate endocrine and *pranshakti*.

6] Halasana

Effects – improved function of thyroid, liver and spleen, pancrease, Reduction of abdominal girth and loss of weight occur. Digestion is improved. Beneficial in diabetes. Mental stress is relieves.

7] Sarvangasana

Effects – increase blood flow of head and neck.

8] Pawanmuktasana

Effects - Improve digestion and relive *vayu*.

9] Pschimottasana

Effects – according to Hath *yogaprdipika* –Activate *pranvayu* in posterior part of body, burn abdominal fat and other yogic text mention the improve digestion preventive for pre-diabetic, strengthen the lungs.

Madhumeha (Diabetes Mellitus)

Madhumeha which is a type of *Vataj Prameha* is generally correlated with Diabetes Mellitus. The WHO has projected that India has a fastest growing diabetic population. it can be included is Maharoga as it affects most vital organs of human body and every cell of human physiology. The main cause of it are lack of exercise and improper food habits such as excessive intake of food having properties like sheeta, snigdha, and guru which increase kapha, meda, and mutra. Tridosha are involved in Prameha and Diwashayan is told to be one of cause for its vitiation.^[12] The kaphakari Aahar vihar, laziness, intake of food which is cold, unctus, sweet, fatty and liquid is causative factors for Pramehas per Charaka and Sushruta.^[13] The general feature of Prameha is Prubhuta and Avila Mutrata. Medodushti symptoms like excessive urination and turbidity. The Ojas in healthy person determines the physical, psychic, sensory and motor function of the body. Dhatukshaya in Prameha leads to imbalance of Oja which may lead to cardiac and nervous disorders.^[14]

The detailed treatment of Prameha is given in ancient compendia according to Doshik predominance. Apart from this in Charak Chikitsasthana had mentioned exercise and other regimens for Prameha. These patients can be cured effectively by different types of exercise, bath, sprinkling of water over the body and application of ointment made by ushira twaka, ela, agaru, chandana etc.^[15]

DISCUSSION

The treatment of Prameha is categorized into two groups based on morphology as per Ayurvedic perspective that is Sthul Pramehi and Krush Pramehi. Sushruta also mentioned that all types of Prameha if not treated properly within the time period it leads to formation of Madhumeha which is incurable. The great key is provided by Sushruta that Madhumeha can be identified in early stage and can be prevented by proper treatment of Prameha. According to Ayurvedic treatment point of view it can be said that no single therapy can work on Diabetes mellitus and there is need to integrate the multiple treatments for it. The entire words is looking towards Yoga for solution to many health problem of the society.

After the detailed review of literature related to yogasana it can be said that some Aasana are very useful in treating Diabetes Mellitus. The probable mode of action and utility can be explained as follows-Anatomically yogic practice maintains muscle strength and bone density, joint flexibility and improves posture, balance and mobility. Yogis were benefited by regular practice of yoga which maintains circulatory and respiratory health, muscle strength, tone, posture with improvement in blood glucose and hematological profile. Asanas, when practicing along with pranayama and dhyana over a period of time, significantly reduce the metabolic rate due to decreased sympathetic nervous system activity.^[16] Heart disease, type 2 diabetes, arteriosclerosis, atherosclerosis, liver disease, elevated cholesterol and hypertension, are the medical conditions associated with insulin insensitivity and elevated blood glucose level, it can be suggested that exercise, relaxation, and stress reduction cause weight loss and increase in insulin sensitivity which is by possible Asana.

The long term Yoga practice in patients with diabetes causes marked drop in the level of hyperglycemia, glycosulated hemoglobin. Similarly in a study conducted by Hegde et al. on the effect of three months yoga practice on oxidative stress in type 2 diabetics conclude that, yoga practionar achieved significant improvement in body mass index, fasting blood glucose level, post – prandial blood glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin, glutathione and vitamin –c at 3 months compared with the standard care group. The increase in hemoglobin explain the

cardio-protective role of yoga by improving cell oxygenation through supplying red blood cells richer in hemoglobin, without increasing the percentage of red blood cells and blood viscosity.^[17] Many prior studies have reported the beneficial effect of the practice of yoga on diabetes. Some studies have mentioned up to 65 percent beneficial effect of yogic therapy for diabetes. K.N. Udupa have even mentioned 5 cases of juvenile diabetes that were completely controlled by yogic treatment. All of these studies have emphasized the possible mechanism of the yogic practices as-

- 1] Reduction in blood sugar due to muscular exercise involved in the Aasanas.
- 2] The effects of walking, treadmill, static cycling and Amarantha Kokkuasana (sitting crane) Nidra Kokkuasana (standing crane) and Vilasana (bow pose, rocking, especially side to side) were compared. In study conducted by S.S. A.Ramaiah in Washington and the most effective were found to be the latter. It was concluded that the direct stimulation of the pancreases by this posture rejuvenated its capacity to produce insulin.
- 3] Direct influences on pancreatic secretion by rejuvenation of the pancreatic cells through alternate abdominal contraction and relaxation during Aasanas and breathing exercises.
- 4] Several studies have focused upon why the practice of yoga has been more successful than other forms of exercise. M. V. Bhole and K.N. Udupa have measured the effect of yoga on mental stresses.^[18]

Aasana- Another study from New Delhi on diabetes, researchers tried to find out if yogasana could help diabetes by releasing insulin from the pancreases, twenty healthy young volunteers were given four sets of yoga postures to perform as follows.

- 1] Dhanurasana (bow pose) & Matsyendrasana (seated twist)
- 2] Halasana (plow pose) & vajrasana (thunderbolt pose)
- 3] Naukasana (boat pose) & Bhujangasana (cobra pose)
- 4] Setubandhasana (bridge pose) & Pavanmuktasana (wind relieving pose).

Each volunteer performed the above sets in random order for five days with two day interval between consecutive sets of Aasanas. Based on blood test results, the authors found that performance of yoga posture lead to improved sensitivity was due to the cumulative effect of the volunteers performing the Asanas.

In 2005 study, 20 patients with type2 diabetes were put on a 40 days yoga routine exercise including Surya Namaskar, Trikonasana, Sukhasana, Padmasana, Paschimottasana, Ardhamatsyendrasana, Pavanmuktasana, Bhujangasana, Vajrasana, Dhanurasana, Shavasana,

Bhastrika Pranayama. At the end of the 40 days, on average the study participant had decrease in fasting glucose levels, a significant decrease in waist hip ratio and beneficial changes in insulin levels.

In order to investigate the effect of Asana and breathing exercise on serum fat (Cholesterol, triglyceride, HDL & LDL) and blood sample of patients after 8 to 12 hours of fasting where used .3 months Yoga session was performed including breathing exercises and meditation sessions in first 10 minutes and followed by the Aasanas with an empty stomach. Some of the common Asana performed in different postures were 1. Vrikshasana 2. Trikonasana 3. Suryanamaskara 4. Vajrasana 5. Baddhakonasana 6. Shashankasana 7. Parvatasana 8. Bhujangasana 9. Dhanurasana and 10. Makarasana. The Sudarshankriya yoga (SKY) is a rhythmical cyclical breathing done in Vajrasana posture with eyes closed and breathing through nostrils was also subjected to participants. The result of this work indicate that, 10 - weeks yoga training has positive effects on total cholesterol, triglycerides, in patients with type 2 diabetes.^[19]

Massaging the Internal organs: postures (particularly the twisting postures) compresses the abdomen against the thigh and induces stomach breathing, as a result the internal organs (Kidney, Liver, Pancrease. etc) are massaged, speeding up the blood circulation and cleansing effect (removal of toxins, blood is the carrier of the toxins as well as the nutrients) similarly massaging of the pancreas will happen which will rejuvenate it and increase the production of pancreatic cell and the insulin.

Reduction in stress: Stress is a major contributing factor to diabetes. Stress increases the secretion of glucagon which is responsible for increasing the blood glucose levels. Stress also release cortisol, adrenaline which can trigger food cravings it few minutes a day practice with a combination of the yogaasana, pranayama, and meditation helps to reduce stress in the mind and body.

Weight loss and lower blood pressure: High intensity sequences like the Suryanamaskara can help to reduce weight and extra fat which in term will keep the blood pressure in check. Also sequences like Suryanamaskara will burn the glucose and the fats decreasing the sugar level in the body. The sequence of Asanas like Utthita parsvakonasana, parivrtta parsvakonasana, Paschimottanasana, Janushirshasana, Makarasana, Dhanurasana, Halasana, Ardhamatsyendrasana, Shashankasana, are helpful in diabetic cases.^[20]

Yogic practices may promote significant improvements in several indices of major importance in the management of the DM2, including glycaemic control lipid levels, and body composition. More limited data suggest that yoga may also lower oxidative stress and blood pressure ,enhance pulmonary and nervous system function, improve mood, sleep, and quality of the life and reduce medication use in adults with DM2.^[21]

The literature review and studies conducted on yogasana confirms many beneficial effects on our body. The mode of action of yoga as described earlier reveals that it acts on various body systems at different level. The disturbed metabolism of ingested meal is the main cause of Diabetes mellitus and practice of yoga set it right by improving digestion .it can be said both Asana have synergistic effect on our body and have beneficial effects for diabetic patients.

CONCLUSION

Contemporary science has focused upon diabetes as only a physical disorder, requiring only physical modalities of intervention. Ayurved and other researches in India had recognized it as psychosomatic disorder with causative factors being sedentary habits, physical, emotional and mental stress many studies have confirmed that the practice of yogasana can rejuvenate the insulin producing cell in the pancreases by pressure over abdominal viscera and back are very helpful for reliving the symptoms.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.who.int/new-room/fact-sheets/detail/diabetes>
2. Park K. Parks Textbook of Preventive and Social Med. 18th edition. Banarasidas Banot Publishers, Jabalpur India, 2005; 311-15.
3. Udupa K<NA manual of science philosophy of Yoga, Reprint ed Varanasi, Sarvodaya Sahitya Prakashan, 2008; 37.
4. Tripathi R, Patanjali –Yogdarshan, Hindi commentary Prathmopadesha, 2nd. Varanasi: Chowkhamba krishnadas Academy, 2010; 12.
5. gaud S, Svasthavrittam, chapter 26,5th ed. Rohtak:Naath Pustak Bhandar, 2005; 298.
6. Rao MV, the essence of Yoga, Yoga down the ages, 1st ed.Varanasi: Chaukhamba orientalia, 2011; 26.
7. Tripathi HHP, Hathyogapradipika, "Hari" Hindi commentary, samadhipada 3rded Varanasi Chowkhamba Krishnadas Acadamy, 2007; 10.
8. Patrikar V, Swathavritta Vidnyan, Vol.2, Aasana(5), 1st Edition, Nagpur: Godavari Publisher; 2005; 41.

9. Ibidem-Rao-M.V (6): 88.
10. Ibidem Tripathi HHP, Hathyogapradipika, 14: 15.
11. Arora N, Svasthavrittam, Aasana 1st ed Varanasi Chaukhmbha Prakashan, 2010; 324-327.
12. Shastri A, Abhinav Swasthavrutta Reprint ed Varanasi; Chaukhambha Prakashan; 2007; 183.
13. Byadgi PS & Pandey AK, Prameha Chikitsa, A textbook of Kaychikitsa 1st ed New Delhi Chaukhambha Publication, 2014; 684.
14. Suresh babu The principles & practice of Kaychikitsa voi-2 Chapter -51 Reprint ed Varanasi; Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2009; 397.
15. Ibidem Byadgi T S & Pandey AK (16): 701.
16. Sachin G. Khedekar et al, Maintenance of sympathovagal balance in disease of Annavaaha Srotas through Yogic Nadis; A Review, Int. J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm., Jan – Feb 2017; 8(1): 4-7.
17. Sharma N, Gupta N. Effect of Yoga on glycaemic profile in diabetics. Int J Med Sci Public Health, 2014; 3: 1135–1140.
18. Health Administrator, Part 1 1; clinical Research on the Benefits of Yoga Practice on Diabetes, 2009; XXII (1&2): 42-45.
19. Balaji PV, Thirumaran M, Effects of 10 Weeks Yoga Training On Blood Glucose and Lipid Profile in Type II Diabetics Patients Sch. J. App. Med. Sci., 2015; 3(5A): 1876–1879.
20. [http://pranayoga.c.in/asana/how -Yoga - heip - in diabetes/](http://pranayoga.c.in/asana/how-Yoga-heip-in-diabetes/)Last access date: 31.07.2017
21. Kim E. Inner and Terry Kit Self, Yoga for Adults with Type 2 Diabetes: A Systematic Review of Controlled Trials, Journal of Diabetes Research, 2016; 1-23.